

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KACHO TAH****FIRST NAME: CHARLES****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2019 on Windows 10)

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Structure and process of academic essay writing (EUCLID 2021, 6-14)
2. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 15-23)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2021, 40-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

This response paper covers the main concepts discussed in the ACA-401D course pack for period one. I studied the course pack with great interest to learn and gain skills in academic writing, which is critical to completing a Doctor of Philosophy program. The content of the course pack is elaborate, clear, and a good guide for students. Complete assimilation and correct use of this content will improve as one writes more papers.

The response paper highlights salient elements of academic essay writing, including the structure and process, punctuations, American vs. British English, plagiarism, style guide, abbreviations, and expressions. These elements are organized and discussed in separate sections under main headings.

2) STRUCTURE AND PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

An academic essay is a writing produced for academic purposes and often published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (EUCLID 2021, 7). Writing an academic essay entails identifying a topic, researching the topic, organizing ideas, writing, referencing, editing, and handing in the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7 – 11). Writing an excellent academic essay includes understanding the topic, defining the question, analyzing the task and answer to the key question, and drafting an initial plan for answering the question and the type of information needed (EUCLID 2021, 7 – 8). Following a structured process in writing an academic essay helps the thinking process, clarifies your research question, organizes ideas, and logical and coherent writing.

After determining a topic, the student will require reading and research to define the key questions and answers and to determine the task involved in completing the essay (EUCLID 2021, 7 - 8). Reading should fill the knowledge gap regarding what the student knows and what more to learn to address the key questions, support the answers or argument and write the essay. Students need to have a strategy to review material quickly, to determine if they are relevant to the topic, and to provide backing to his/her hypothesis and answers. There is a need to keep the topics and key questions in mind during reading and identify relevant information such as central arguments, direct quotations, examples, case studies, and statistics that provide evidence and strengthens one's argument (EUCLID 2021, 9).

Creative and critical thinking is essential for essay writing; the student should employ these when reading. Creative thinking enables the student to explore his/her ideas further, for example, through deep brainstorming or reflections (EUCLID 2021, 9). Creative thinking is crucial as it enables the student to stay on his/her original ideas and not submit to confusion from exposure to tons of knowledge often available on the subject during reading. Critical thinking encourages one to narrow the focus or scope of his/her ideas to review and validate the ideas or check alternative reasoning. As such, the student should strive to write a balanced essay that considers perspectives from other authors and evidence that do not agree with their argument (EUCLID 2021, 9). If arguments differ, a review of why one adheres to one and not the other need to be discussed and linked to the conclusion of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 9).

As in any vital writing, the organization of ideas is essential. Reading and researching help develop ideas and provides relevant insights to inform the planning of an essay. The plan should include possible answers to the question, the information needed to answer it, evidence to support the answer, and a sketch of points to discuss, including the order (EUCLID 2021, 9).

Writing the essay is the next step after establishing a solid plan. The essay structure comprises an introduction, body, and conclusion (EUCLID 2021, 10). An introduction mainly highlights what the essay will discuss. The introduction begins with general and then narrows down to specifics, starts with a broad opening statement of the topic area, and

then the thesis statement and ends with a summary or road map of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10). The body comprises paragraphs that develop your argument using the evidence gathered (EUCLDI 2021, 10).

Contrary to an introduction, a conclusion moves from specific to general, recapping the answer to the question, and the main points of an argument and ending with implications, and opportunities for further research related to the subject, without introducing new information or knowledge (EUCLDI 2021, 10). An essay wraps up with references. Referencing is mandatory for all academic papers.

Prior to finalizing and submitting an academic essay, students are encouraged to conduct thorough editing. Editing helps improve an academic paper; therefore, it is necessary to exercise prudence to address new perspectives, information, and deficiencies observed (EUCLID 2021, 11). During editing, try to check if your answer addresses the question clearly and thoroughly, whether the argument is coherent, whether the evidence is relevant, and whether the citation style is consistent (EUCLID 2021, 12).

3) PUNCTUATIONS

Correct punctuation is necessary to clarify a sentence's intended meaning. Punctuations may seem easy, but some are very difficult to apply. Generally, in academic and other formal writing, it is advisable to limit punctuation (EUCLID 2021, page 16). Frequently used punctuations include apostrophes, brackets, bullet points, colon and semicolon, commas, dashes and hyphens, ellipsis, full stops, exclamation marks, question signs, and quotation marks.

An apostrophe is relatively easy to use in most cases. We often add apostrophes after singular or plural nouns, which do not end with s to indicate possession, for example, Peter's car, or to indicate that letters have been omitted, for example, can't for cannot (EUCLID 2021, page 16).

Regarding brackets, there are four types, i.e., round: (), square: [], angle: <>, and curly: {} brackets. People commonly use round brackets and rarely use others, possibly due to their complexity. Writers are also creative and have alternatives for brackets. One frequent use of round brackets is to provide extra information, a translation, dates, an explanation, or a definition (EUCLID 2021, page 16). For example, the traveler (who discovered the diamonds in Congo) was a Belgian. The use of square brackets is different from round brackets. Use square brackets to enclose comments, corrections, references, or translations made by a subsequent author or editor (EUCLID 2021, page 17). Angle brackets and curly brackets are appropriate for use for technical purposes only (EUCLID 2021, page 17).

Bullet points can be beneficial in presenting a list of items, elements, and facts. A common mistake is finding punctuation at the bullet point's end. However, it is correct to have a complete stop at the end in case the bullet points form a complete sentence with preceding text (EUCLID 2021, page 17).

It is essential to learn how to use all punctuation. EUCLID (2021 17-20) provides explanations and examples of when and how to use various punctuation. As examined in this course pack, one can use punctuation differently. Some include; the colon and semicolon used to introduce a text that links logically to the one before it; for example, the ceremony took place in the enormous amphitheater: Magenta (EUCLID 2021, 17). Commas can be used to border a defining clause; for example, the warehouse, which served as a cocoa storage facility for forty years, will be demolished (EUCLID 2021, 19). Dashes and hyphens help improve the writing and readability of a sentence. One can use a pair of n-dash (-) instead of round brackets or commas. For example, the traveler - who discovered the diamonds in Congo - was a Belgian. A hyphen, on its part, is used in various situations, including in an adjectival phrase before a noun (e.g., up-to-date), in an adjectival phrase including a verb participle (e.g., his pant was tight-fitting), with prefixes before a proper name, number or date (e.g., anti-Racism) (EUCLID 2021, 20). Ellipsis shows that some text is missing, usually from a quotation (EUCLID 2021, 20). The use of full stop, exclamation mark, and question mark are evident. We use them only at the end of a sentence.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

The difference between Standard American English and standard British English is only sometimes apparent. While some of the differences are common, many are unknown to several people. I mix the two sometimes in an essay. Using any of them in essay writing is acceptable as the chosen one is used consistently across the essay. Some essential differences between American and British English are concerning; the difference in pronunciation given the exact spelling, for example, of words like; advertisement, controversy, laboratory, secretary, leisure, schedule, dynasty, and dance; difference in spelling, although pronunciation might be the same for example, organization — organisation, cheque — check, color — colour (EUCLID 2021, 20). There are also instances where the terms are the same, but the spelling is different such as aluminum — aluminium (EUCLID 2021, 20).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is when one uses a source of information (words or ideas written, often quoted, paraphrased, or copied) without giving credit to the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2021, 34). Avoiding plagiarism when writing a paper is very important, and one can achieve this by properly citing the author or source of information being used (EUCLID 2021, 34). While this may sound easy, it can be challenging to avoid for those with limited academic writing experience. Even when paraphrasing, there is a need to use different words and styles from that of the author, making this a somewhat difficult task. Students need to learn tips on how to paraphrase.

There is in-text citation, which means citing the work you are using within the actual text and using quotation marks (EUCLID 2021, 34). Regarding longer quotations,

present them as separate short paragraphs without quotation marks. A list of works cited should be included at the bottom of the essay. In the case of a book, the format used is; the Authors Name. Date. Book Title. Place of Publication: Publisher. (EUCLID 2021, 38). For online works, it is; Author. Title of the site, name of editors listed, the date the URL was accessed, and the URL in brackets. The course pack presents how to paraphrase materials from different sources.

6)STYLE GUIDE

The style guide has to do with how one writes and formats an essay and therefore goes beyond the correct use of grammar, punctuation, and vocabulary (EUCLID 2021, 41). It includes elements like sentence lengths, manuscript layout, font, depth of treatment of a subject, spelling (US vs. UK), readability, use of abbreviations, use of symbols, voice preference (active vs. passive), structure, terminology, paragraph numbering, use of headings, use of lists) (EUCLID 2021, 41). Style guide improves the quality of a piece of work and can help significantly reduce the time it takes to proofread and correct the work (EUCLID 2021, 42).

EUCLID recommends the Chicago Style (Turabian) for formatting research papers. Chicago Style prescribes how to use abbreviations and acronyms, capitalization, compound words, emphasis, numbers and dates, title and text page, footnotes, headings, lists, bibliography, tables, and table notes. (EUCLID 2021, 42). It might require a few essays writings practice to acquaint myself thoroughly with the Turabian rule of style, and I am confident the coursepack will be very helpful for this end.

7)CONCLUSION

Good academic essay writing follows a logical process and complies with standard grammar guidelines and style. Students need to exercise diligence in writing an essay that meets acceptable standards. For any academic essay writing process, one needs to have a topic, research the topic, and plan the essay before writing the essay. EUCLID recommends the Turabian Style for formatting research papers. The course pack provides comprehensive and essential details on this style. Correct punctuations are critical to readability and understanding of the piece of writing. In writing, a student needs to choose American Standard English or British Standard English and be consistent with using the chosen one throughout the essay. Plagiarism is intolerable, and students should take the necessary precaution and find ways to avoid it. The course pack is technically demanding, and one may achieve total mastery by writing more papers.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.